

Quality Oriented Management

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ABSTRACT

Quality management is a phenomenon. Advanced culture that supports arts and crafts allows shoppers to choose goods with higher quality standards compared to the normal stuff. In a society that appreciates the arts and crafts, one of the tasks of the management company or owner of the company is the head of the workshop, as well as train and supervise employees and interns. The company sets the standard, assesses the work of the employees and orders rework or repair is necessary. Jobs in crafts have a limitation that is only capable of producing little other products, but has the advantage that each product can be made independently in accordance with the wishes of the customer. Craft work approach towards quality score is the primary input when the initial establishment of quality management as a part of management science.

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, quality can be defined as anything that is able to meet customer needs and expectations, or the suitability between customer needs and the company's offerings. The higher the quality of the product, the higher the customer satisfaction with the product. Product or service excellence can be measured through the level of customer satisfaction (Ariani, 2021)

The industrial revolution replaced the craft work approach with mass production and repetitive work aimed at producing the same goods in large quantities. The initial proponent in the United States of this approach was Eli Whitney, when he advocated the creation of rifle components, which were interchangeable, so as to form a rifle assembly line. The next initiator is Frederick Winslow Taylor, a mechanical engineer who sought improvements in industrial efficiency. Often referred to as the "father of scientific management," he pioneered the idea of the Efficiency Movement which later became part of the foundations of quality management, including aspects of standardization and improvement practices. Henry Ford is also an important figure who implements quality management practices in car assembly lines Ford.

In Germany, Karl Friedrich Benz, who is often referred to as the inventor of the motor vehicle, tried the practice of assembly line production, although mass production was only recently implemented by Volkswagen after the second world war. Since this period, companies in Europe and the United States have focused on production with lower costs and higher efficiency.

A Quality Management System is a system within an organization that can influence customers to try new products offered by the organization, and then remain loyal to continue using the products offered by the organization. The easier it is for customers to get the products offered by the organization through the convenience of the existing system, the more loyal customers will be in using the products offered by the organization.

Therefore, there is a standard for the system implemented by management. The better the system implemented by management in the organization, the easier it will be for the organization to obtain international standards for the implementation of the management system in the organization. ISO 9001:2000 is an international standard for quality management systems. ISO 9001:2000 establishes requirements and recommendations for the design and assessment of quality management systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Quality

According to W. Edward Deming in Chaeriah MM (2016), Quality is conformity with market or consumer needs. A quality company is a company that controls market share because its production results are in accordance with

consumer needs, thereby creating satisfaction for consumers. If consumers are satisfied, then they will be loyal in buying company products in the form of goods and services.

According to Joseph Juran in Ahmad (2020), Quality is the suitability of product use (fitness for use) to meet customer needs and satisfaction. The suitability of the product user is based on five main characteristics, namely (1) technology; namely strength; (2) psychological, namely feeling or status; (3) time, namely reliability; (4) contractual, namely there is a guarantee; (5) ethics, namely good manners.

According to Philip B. Crosby in Sriwidadi (2001), Quality is conformance to requirements, namely in accordance with what is required or standardized. A product has quality if it complies with predetermined quality standards or criteria, these quality standards include raw materials, production processes and finished products.

From these three figures we can conclude that quality is a consumer need for complete customer satisfaction with an item that is needed or quality is a measure related to customer satisfaction with a product. Understanding Management Systems Quality according to Gasperz (2002:10) in Tanzihan (2019) are as follows :

"A Quality Management System is a set of documented procedures and standard practices for system management which aims to ensure the suitability of a process and product (goods/services) to the needs or requirements determined or specified by the customer or organization"

A Quality Management System defines how an organization consistently implements quality management practices to meet customer and market needs.

Meanwhile, according to Stephen (1997) in Tistogondo & Kurniawan (2016) ISO 9001:2000 is defined as follows: "ISO 9001:2000 is concerned with specifying requirements for a quality system. A quality system is composed of an organizational structure, documented procedures, and tools. The goal is to present attributes of the organization's structure, procedures and/or tools that must be present in order to satisfy the requirements of ISO 9001:2000"

Quality Management Systems explains that ISO 9001:2000 relates to Quality Management Systems. The Quality Management System is formed from the organizational structure, documentation, procedures and tools contained within the organization. And the aim is to provide transparency regarding organizational structures, procedures and organizational tools which can then provide satisfaction to consumers.

In this case, from the two definitions previously mentioned, it can be said that a quality management system is a tool implemented in an organization, which is applied to provide transparency regarding activities within the organization. This activity is expected to provide satisfaction and meet the needs of customers and the market.

METHODOLOGY

Research purposes

This research aims to explore the relationship between culture that supports arts and crafts and quality management in a business context. This research will explore how culture, arts and crafts influence the selection of high quality products, the role of management in ensuring quality and approaches to quality assessment in the crafts business.

Method of collecting data

1. Structured Interview

Structured interviews will be conducted with business owners, managers and employees in various craft companies that are in strong cultural, arts and crafts settings. Interviews were conducted to gain in-depth insight into the role of management in ensuring product quality, the efforts made to maintain culture, arts and crafts as well as the role of training and supervision of quality.

2. Consumer Survey

Surveys will be given to customers who frequently purchase arts and crafts products. The survey will include questions about factors that influence the selection of high-quality products, their perceptions of quality products and whether culture, arts and crafts influence their shopping.

3. Company Document Analysis

Analysis will be carried out on internal company documents, such as quality guidelines, inspection records, improvement reports and policies related to quality management. This will really help understand the implementation of quality management practices in the company.

Data Analysis Method

The data collected will be analyzed using various methods, including:

- Thematic Analysis

The results of the interviews will be analyzed thematically to identify key patterns in management roles, quality management practices, culture, arts and crafts.

- Statistic analysis

Consumer survey data will be analyzed statistically with the help of software to identify trends, correlations and significant relationships between the variables studied.

- Document Analysis

Internal company documents will be examined and analyzed to understand the extent to which quality and quality-related practices are implemented.

RESEARCH RESULT

It is hoped that the results of this research will provide a deeper understanding of the relationship between culture, arts and crafts and quality management in a business context. Some of the findings are as follows:

- Identify the key role of management in maintaining and improving product quality in culture, arts and crafts.
- An understanding of how culture, arts and crafts can influence consumers' selection of high-quality products.
- Findings about the most effective quality management practices in craft businesses that prioritize quality.
- Advice for craft companies wishing to improve their quality management in the context of culture, arts and crafts.

DISCUSSION

Quality Management System Objectives

According to Gasperz (2002) in Budiono (2014) The objectives of the quality management system are as follows:

1. Guarantee the suitability of a process and product to certain needs or requirements; Conformity between the needs and requirements set out in a particular standard for the processes and products produced by the company is very important. 2. Providing satisfaction to consumers through fulfilling the needs and process and product requirements determined by customers and the organization; Customer decisions are customers' positive emotional and rational reactions. To be able to provide satisfaction to customers, all organizational personnel are required to have competence in carrying out their respective duties and responsibilities.

Several steps in implementing a quality management system

The implementation of a process in an organization usually has several steps, in the case of implementing a quality management system according to Gasperz (2002) the sequence given is only a guide, which can be carried out simultaneously or in an arrangement that does not have to be sequential, depending on culture and maturity. organization, but all these steps must be taken seriously and consistently. And the steps are as follows: 1. Decide to adopt a quality management system standard that will be implemented. The quality management system standards are selected based on and in accordance with customer needs. In this regard, the ISO 9001:2000 quality management system can be chosen. 2. Establish a commitment at the senior leadership level of the organization (top management commitment). Implementation of a quality management system requires commitment from organizational management and all quality management system standards require this commitment to be documented. An organization's commitment to quality can

be demonstrated from the start through the signing of an organizational quality policy statement, and this is followed by consistent management attitudes and behavior in implementing work procedures. 3. Establish a working group or steering committee consisting of senior managers. All senior managers must actively participate and properly understand the standard requirements of the quality management system. 4. Assign management representatives. The organization shall assign a management representative, who is free from other responsibilities, and must define authority and responsibility to ensure that the quality management system requirements are implemented and maintained. 5. Establish quality objectives and system implementation. There is no standard or single method of implementing a quality management system in an organization. However, the implementation program (work procedures) must be the responsibility of all members of the organization and carried out correctly from the start. 6. Review the current quality management system. In this regard, it is necessary to carry out a system audit or assessment of the existing quality management system. 7. Define organizational structure and responsibilities. The development of a quality management system presents an ideal opportunity for an organization to conduct a detailed evaluation and review the existing management structure. 8. Create quality awareness at all levels in the organization. Quality awareness can be raised through a series of training on quality to answer the questions: what is quality?, why is it necessary to have a quality management system?, what is a quality manual?, why should the quality management system be documented in system procedures and work procedures detailed?, what is an organization's quality policy?, why does cooperation need to be implemented in implementing a quality management system?, and so on. 9. Develop a review of the quality management system in a quality manual (guidebook). This relates to a brief review of the quality management system and whether the required policies and documents are complete and neatly arranged in the management system. 10. Agree that functions and activities are controlled by procedures. In this regard, it is necessary to develop a flow diagram of the organization's business activities and determine the critical things that will influence the success of the organization. 11. Document detailed activities in operational procedures or detailed procedures. This relates to documents specific to products, activities or processes and must be placed at the work location so that they are easy to read by the employees or workers involved. 12. Introducing documentation once the quality manual and procedures have been agreed upon, then the implementation of quality management system practices at the management level can take place. 13. Establish employee participation and training in the system. This stage will be very important for the success and efficiency of the quality management system. 14. Review and audit the quality management system. A review of the quality management system is necessary to ensure conformity with the standard requirements of the quality management system. Review and audit the quality management system. A review of the quality

management system is necessary to ensure conformity with the standard requirements of the quality management system. Review and audit the quality management system. A review of the quality management system is necessary to ensure conformity with the standard requirements of the quality management system.

Benefits of Implementing a Quality Management System

Implementing a process in an organization always has benefits, and according to Gasperz (2002; 17) in Rosdiyanti & Khairunnisah (2022) There are several benefits from implementing a quality management system, namely: 1. Increasing customer trust and satisfaction through organized and systematic quality assurance. The documentation process in ISO 9001:2000 shows that policies, procedures and instructions relating to quality have been well planned. 2. Companies that have been certified to ISO 9001:2000 are permitted to advertise in the mass media that the company's quality management system has been recognized internationally. This means improving the company's image and competitiveness in entering the global market. 3. Audits of the quality management system of companies that have obtained ISO 9001:2000 certificate are carried out periodically to ensure registration from the registration agency so that customers do not need to audit the quality management system. This will save costs and reduce duplication of quality management system audits by customers. 4. Companies that have obtained the ISO 9001:2000 certificate are automatically registered with the registration agency, so that if potential customers want to find suppliers who are ISO 9001:2000 certified, they will contact the registration agency. If the company has been registered with an international registration institution, then this means it opens up new market opportunities. 5. Improving quality and productivity through better cooperation and communication, consistent control systems, as well as reducing and preventing waste due to better internal operations. 6. Increase quality awareness within the company. 7. Provide systematic training to all employees and managers of the organization through well-defined procedures and instructions. 8. There has been a positive change in terms of the quality culture of members of the organization, because management and employees are encouraged to maintain the ISO 9001:2000 certificate, which is generally only valid for three years.

Contribution to Company Quality Management.

According to W. Edward Deming in Hidayat (2007) Quality problems lie in management problems, in this case quality is faced by the company so it must be measured from things related to management.

There are 14 W. Edward Deming points in Rahman (2020) which is well-known and is a new combination of quality management and a call for management to change its approach, namely: 1. Create a business to improve

products and services with the aim of being competitive and continuing to operate and providing job vacancies. 2. Adopt a new philosophy. 3. Avoid dependence on mass inspection to achieve quality. 4. End the practice of pricing businesses on price. 5. Constantly improve production and service systems to increase quality and productivity. 6. Institute job training. 7. Institute leadership. 8. Eliminate fear so that everyone can work effectively. 9. Describe the obstacles between departments. 10. Eliminate slogans, pressures and targets and increase productivity without increasing workload. 11. Eliminate work standards that use numerical quotas. 12. Remove obstacles that rob employees of pride in their skills. 13. Institute various education/training programs that increase enthusiasm and improve work quality. 14. Put everyone in a work team so they can carry out the transformation.

Of the fourteen points stated by W. Edward Deming above, they are analyzed or seen from consumer satisfaction, in this case what is meant is the company's employees and company stakeholders.

In planning company quality, Joseph Juran uses Quality Management approach Management (Strategic Quality Management) is widely discussed and applied nowadays.

SQM (Strategic Quality Management), is a three-part process based on staff at different levels making unique contributions to quality improvement. Company leaders have a strategic view of the organization or institution, deputy leaders have an operational view of quality, and managers also have responsibility for quality control.

SQM (Strategic Quality Management), is suitable to be applied in a company context in line with the idea of Consultant at Work by John Miller in an effort to improve company quality. John Miller believes that senior management (the Board of Directors) needs to use strategic quality management by developing the company's vision, priorities and policies.

Joseph Juran in RIFAN (2019) introduces three quality processes, including the following: 1. Quality planning which includes customer quality, determining customer needs, setting quality targets, and improving process capabilities. 2. Quality control, consisting of choosing the basis of control, choosing the type of measurement, developing work standards, and measuring actual performance, 3. Quality improvement, consisting of: identifying specific improvements, organizing institutions to diagnosing errors, finding the cause of the error increasing the need to make improvements.

Joseph Juran believes that the use of an approach to improve the quality of education must be step by step because all forms of quality improvement must be carried out in a step by step manner.

According to Joseph Juran, the quality management components above systematically include the following: 1. Building awareness of needs and opportunities for development. 2. Develop clear goals for development. 3.

Creating an organizational structure to carry out the development process. 4. Provide appropriate training. 5. Take a problem-solving approach. 6. Identify and report implementation. 7. Know success. 8. Communicate results. 9. Report changes and 10. Develop annual improvements to all company operational processes.

In managing the quality and performance of the company, a leader should pay attention to the components above, apart from that he must evaluate the extent of success that has been carried out in relation to The Juran Trilogy planning regarding quality (Quality Planning), quality control (Quality Control), and improvement. as well as quality improvement.

B. Philip Crosby stated that a systematic step to achieve quality will produce good quality. A company's savings will come naturally when the company does everything correctly, always trying to be careful in every step that includes input, such as teaching materials (cognitive, affective and psychomotor), methodology, infrastructure and other resources. Meanwhile, quality in the context of company performance refers to the achievements achieved by the company in each certain period.

There are 14 steps in Philip B. Crosby Riyuzen (2018) to achieve company quality management, namely: 1. Management Commitment. 2. Building a Quality Improvement Team (Quality Improvement Team). 3. Quality Measurement (Quality Measurements). 4. Measuring the Cost of Quality (The Cost of Quality). v5. Building Quality Awareness. 6. Corrective Action. 7. Zero Defects Planning. 8. Emphasize the need for supervisor training. 9. Organizing Zero Defects Day. 10. Goal Setting. 11. Error Cause Removal. 12. Recognition. 13. Establish Quality Councils. 14. Do It Over Again. If you compare the studies of W. Edward Deming, Joseph Juran and Philip B. Crosby, you will find several similarities and differences.

The similarities are: 1. They consider that customers, both internal and external, are important. 2. The manager's role is the main responsibility for improving quality. 3. Recognize that there is a quality crisis that must immediately be corrected or improved through several actions. 4. In looking at the importance of quality, Philip Crosby highlights quality habits in organizations, while W. Edward Deming shows the obsession with quality in order to provide satisfaction to customers and other implications that can also keep organizations in a situation that tends to be competitive. 5. Prefer concrete actions rather than just using slogans and warnings. 6. Training is an investment for the future. 7. Active participation in problem solving efforts. 8. Use of techniques and scientific knowledge. 9. Education and training are important. 10. The importance of improving quality continuously, W. Edward Deming calls it doing it continuously and forever while Philip Crosby calls it repeating itself. 11. The need for a quality control organization. 12. The role of leadership is the main responsibility for improving quality.

The differences are as follows: 1. W. Edward Deming places more emphasis on management which is quite tough compared to Philip Crosby. 2. The approach taken by W. Edward Deming is more specific and Philip Crosby's is more general. 3. W. Edward Deming proposed the need to look for key or main issues that would be followed up with continuous improvement and based on the concept of optimism in a comprehensive system, on the other hand, Philip Crosby, after finding the main issues, followed up with a quality trilogy, namely planning, monitoring and improvement. 4. W. Edward Deming was more concerned with the concept of education while Philip Crosby prioritized building the parts and detailing the implementation. 5. W. Edward Deming focused more on management and processes than on graduation while Philip Crosby was more concerned with results. 6. W. Edward Deming firmly believes that quality management and responsibility for corrective action is directed at all employees, while Philip Crosby emphasizes that responsibility for quality lies with middle managers. 7. Seeing the reality of most companies today which are faced with various forms of competition, therefore efforts to improve the quality or quality of company performance are highly prioritized.

At the end of this discussion it can be stated:

1. Integrated Quality Management (Total Quality Management, TQM) is an effort to meet customer needs at the lowest possible cost.
2. There are several definitions of quality put forward by several quality pioneers, including Frederick W. Taylor, Walter A. Shewhart, David A. Garvin, Edward Deming, and Philip B. Crosby.
3. The definition of quality according to Philip B. Crosby is conformity to requirements.
4. There are four postulates of quality according to Philip B. Crosby as follows:
 - a. The definition of quality is conformity to requirements.
 - b. The quality system is prevention.
 - c. The work standard is Zero Defect.
 - d. Quality measurement is the cost of quality (Price of Nonconformance, PONC)

CONCLUSION

From the description above it can be concluded: 1. According to W. Edward Deming, quality is conformity with market or consumer needs. A quality company is a company that controls market share because its production results are in accordance with consumer needs, thereby creating satisfaction for consumers. If consumers are satisfied, then they will be loyal in buying company products in the form of goods and services. 2. According to Joseph Juran, quality is the suitability of product use (fitness for use) to meet customer needs and satisfaction. The suitability of the product user is based on

five main characteristics, namely (1) technology; namely strength; (2) psychological, namely feeling or status; (3) time, namely reliability; (4) contractual, namely there is a guarantee; (5) ethics, namely good manners. 3. According to Philip B. Crosby, Quality is conformance to requirements, that is, in accordance with what is required or standardized. A product has quality if it complies with predetermined quality standards or criteria, these quality standards include raw materials, production processes and finished products. 4. Quality Management System defines how an organization consistently applies quality management practices to meet customer and market needs. 5. According to Gasperz, System Quality management is a set of documented procedures and standard practices for system management which aims to ensure the suitability of a process and product (goods/services) to the needs or requirements determined or specified by the customer or organization. 6. According to W. Edward Deming, quality problems lie in management problems, in this case the quality faced by educational institutions must be measured from things related to management.

There are 14 points of the famous W. Edward Deming and are a new combination of quality management and a call for management to change its approach. 14 points expressed by Philip Crosby and 3 points by Joseph Juran regarding their contribution to quality management. 8. Based on the theory expressed by W. Edward Deming, Joseph Juran, and Philip B. Crosby regarding the contribution of company quality management strategy, their opinion is very unique and interesting to apply in today's industrial world. They argue that it is quite logical, W. Edward Deming is quite detailed and very clear, in line with the theory expressed by Joseph Juran, namely three aspects as Quality Planning, Quality Control and Quality Improvement, even stronger is the theory expressed by Philip B. Crosby that works without error is very possible.

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This research still has limitations so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic "Quality Oriented Management" to perfect this research, as well as increase insight for readers.

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